

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

USING SOCIAL MEDIA AND DIGITAL TOOLS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

Recently, learning foreign languages using the Internet has become popular. In this regard, there are a number of social networks that have created special conditions for those who want to learn the language. Users who do not know the language very well often try to establish a dialogue in that language. In this case, the assessment and advice of other users will help him. Currently, the use of social networks in the teaching of foreign languages is very relevant and has a positive role in increasing the motivation of students to learn the language. In this regard, recent research shows the growing interest of linguists, historians and politicians in social networks.

Keywords: social media, internet, education, social network.

The Internet is considered the World Wide Web for communication. It connects hundreds of thousands of computer networks. It is considered a communication system that allows computer machines to communicate. Researchers in the field of communication define it as a means of cooperative communication that includes a large number of computer networks worldwide, allowing individuals and groups to use them as a means of communication on a large scale.

Web 2.0 technology is characterized as social, personalized, interactive and participatory. Second language acquisition is considered to have many advantages, particularly in promoting increased learner autonomy and promoting interaction and collaboration. Autonomy and collaboration are at the core of Web 2.0 websites, where users come together to "collaborate, learn, and create knowledge." This collaborative nature of learning is based on a "participatory architecture" that allows users to create content in a public space, such as a social networking site.

The technological and information revolution in various fields of human knowledge has become the most important feature of the twenty-first century. This revolution touched all spheres of life as it contributed to the state of rapprochement and communication, the elimination of geographical boundaries, class and ethnic differences. This has led to a mingling of cultures as well as daily monitoring of events on the world stage.

Social networks are one of the results of these technological developments that have entered our daily lives. Although the primary purpose of creating these sites is social communication between individuals, this use has increasingly spread to include all areas of daily life and all cultural, social, political and economic activities. Thus, social sites have created a new form of free and direct communication. Social media is now being used in more and more areas.

The education sector represents one of these areas that has undergone some degree of change and impact on social networking sites. Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp and other networks are considered to be among the most important methods used and applied in the educational process, because they are a flexible virtual environment and platform where the parties involved in the educational process communicate while

presenting educational models based on strategies that enable information, knowledge and information acquisition. provides. to exchange ideas. In addition, they help to train a generation of teachers and learners with the skills to work with modern technologies and their subsequent developments, as well as to share these skills with the wider community and open doors for equitable education.

L.A. Bekheti stated that there are several reasons for using social media in the classroom:

- Its content supports teaching and learning on a lifelong learning scale; contributes to equity and inclusion and raises standards across Higher Education institutions to improve the quality and accessibility of course content.
- Social media enables students to create digital content and publish it online, increasing the vast resource of user-generated content that students and teachers can benefit from together, and encouraging more active and engaged approaches to learning.
- Social media is a network that connects students and their teachers, allowing them to share their knowledge and at the same time gain access to specialized and targeted knowledge in a particular area of interest.
- Social media enables collaboration between learners and teachers on a specific task or project or a common goal, combines resources and collects the experience of a group of people working towards a common goal [4, p.468].

P.J. Crowley also discusses some of the reasons for using social media in the classroom as follows:

1. Social media provides spaces for students to share their stories both inside and outside the classroom.
2. It also gives them an opportunity to hear stories outside of school.
3. Social media helps students to recognize their personal power [4, p.468].

Another study suggested learning through websites and social networks (such as Facebook) because they are accessible for interaction, collaboration, information and resource sharing. M.N. Amin and others state that social networking sites promote participation and critical thinking [2, p.1]. H.Ajjan and R.Hartshorne

reviewed course content and assessment, cross-cultural language learning and its positive effects on identity expression and digital literacy, especially for marginalized groups and increased peer support and communication [1, p.71].

Currently, the most used social media tools in the field of education are:

1. Blogs. Blogging is used for various educational purposes, such as:

- Publication of research papers and school homework. A hosting system where students use a blogging system electronically instead of the traditional way to publish their research and homework.

- Creating an environment of cooperation and constructive dialogue among students by following and commenting on their colleagues' blogs.

2. Facebook. Educators and students can use Facebook in Education to create a Facebook page or group for educational purposes:

- Inviting teachers and students to participate by sharing and exchanging information and Internet links on educational topics.

- Educational images and videos can be uploaded, then teachers and students can share, discuss and comment on them.

3. Twitter. As a result of research, it was found that Twitter is also widely used in education:

- Further conferences and seminars.

- Update courses; A teacher of any course can create a Twitter account for that course.

- Facilitate project management; Students or instructors working together on a project can communicate with each other using Twitter. They remind each other about project issues and project status

- Activate discussions and debates; Twitter's interactivity can help a group of people by creating channels for debate and discussion on specific topics.

4. Instagram was launched as a photo sharing platform and over time other new features like video, text and story sharing have been added which have greatly contributed to its growth. In terms of language learning, Handayani argues that Instagram can be used as a resource for implementing several activities in language classrooms, such as digital stories, grammar activities through photos, role-playing, reading, speaking activities through videos. Thus, the Instagram language includes four language skills to practice in the classroom and beyond. In addition, some research has been done on Instagram to develop writing skills. These studies have shown that Instagram is an effective tool for improving students' writing skills. In addition, Instagram has been found to increase students' motivation to learn and their participation in classroom activities. Among their studies of the use of Instagram for language learning, Mansor and Rahim found it to be an effective platform that encouraged students to interact with their peers in group work involving videos they shared about teacher-led tasks.

5. WhatsApp. The results of L. Chetinkaya's research showed that students formed positive opinions about the use of WhatsApp in their classes [3]. They tried the same experiment in their other courses. Thus,

they found that learning using WhatsApp can be unconscious and messages with pictures can be more effective for students to learn the language. However, several students expressed negative views about the timing of some posts and the excess posts within the group. Finally, the use of WhatsApp in the educational process has been identified as both a supportive technology for students and also the possibility of encountering potentially harmful friendships. Therefore, first of all, teachers should know how to use social networks and teach students how to use them correctly and positively [4, p. 469-470].

A study conducted by S. Manca and M. Ranieri shows that the use of social media or digital media is more stimulating and motivating [4, p.470]. The applications of social media for teaching and learning have been quite useful as some of the tools can be applied in everyday practice where students take their assignments home. Some options that can be adopted by teachers and students are presented by S. Manca as special communities for class, group work, exchange of ideas and continuous teacher education [4, p.470]. Community resources allow embedding of videos, links, documents, text or voice messages. By using a collaborative space such as social networks, the teacher in turn has the opportunity to improve aspects such as writing skills among students, improving writing development, conducting research on the topic, giving feedback and organizing debate.

Sosial şəbəkələr tələbələrə problem qaldırmağa və yaradıcı olmağa təşviq edərək yeni üsullardan istifadə etməklə tədqiqat və ev tapşırıqları üçün onlardan istifadəyə yönləndirir. Hətta sosial şəbəkələr tələbələrə kitab mübadiləsi və onları bir-birindən borc almağa imkan verir. Sosial şəbəkələr tələbələrin öz müəllimləri ilə ünsiyyətini asanlaşdırmaqla onların sayını artırmağa bilər. Bundan əlavə, sosial şəbəkələr texnologiya mədəniyyətini yayır və tələbələrə öz ixtisasları üzrə ən son yeniliklər haqqında məlumatlandıraraq maarifləndirir. Sosial ünsiyyət vasitələri utancaq tələbələrə öz fikirlərini yazılı şəkildə ifadə etməyə imkan verir ki, bu da onların yaradıcılığını oyatmağa kömək edir.

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